

Factors and Correlates of composite adverse birth outcomes with HIV-Infection and associated co-morbidities among postnatal women attending selected maternal facility, Nairobi, Kenya

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Abstract:

Maternal HIV and related co-morbidities has contributed to several adverse birth out-comes with paucity of data to explain this phenomenon. PMTCT focus on vertical HIV transmission, but no data on poor birth out-comes on HIV and associated morbidities which is a dynamic phenomenon. With a number of studies having investigated correlations of HIV disease with birth outcomes, an extensive assessment using a comparative group(controls) is lacking. In the current study, estimation of HIV and related co-morbidities risks of adverse birth outcomes in among post-natal women was performed with the ultimate outcome being neonatal mortality.

Methodology & Theoretical Orientation: Design was unmatched case control. The information was extracted from records of the study subjects within the first twenty-eight days after birth randomly and considering age, sex, anthropometric measurements and other clinical factors of the newborn and mother. A total of 256 records were reviewed retrospectively on cases and controls at 1:1 ratio. Mothers' pregnancy history, clinical and social economic, co morbidities and health factors were considered for both arms. The data was analyzed using SPSS version 20.0. Chi-square test was used to establish the correlation between the dependent and independent variables at (SS) p-value < 0.05. Multiple logistic regression analyses were performed to adjust for confounding. AOR with corresponding 95% confidence interval was estimated.

Findings: Out of 128 cases (neonatal mortalities) 12.5% were born from HIV-positive mothers compared to 3.9% among 128 controls HIV was significantly correlated with neonatal mortality in bivariate analysis [OR= 3.51; 95%CI: 1.25-9.91; P=0.012] but not sustained after adjusting for other factors at the multivariate analysis [AOR=2.33; 95%CI: 0.76-7.15; P=0.139]. Multiple logistic regression revealed; LBW [AOR= 3.97; 95%CI: 2.26-6.98; P< 0.001], co-morbidities [AOR= 3.84; 95%CI: 1.32- 11.16; P=0.013]. Mother's hemoglobin level [AOR= 3.18; 95%CI: 1.19-8.46; P=0.021], unemployment [AOR=0.43; 95%CI: 0.22-0.85; P=0.016]. There's increased risk of neonatal mortality and related morbidities with HIV infection among postnatal women

Keywords:

Pregnancy, HIV-Diseases, Co-Morbidities, Neonatal Mortality

Figure 1: Figure illustrates the relationship between both predictor and outcome variables, how they are also intervened by the confounders.

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A review of Neonatal Jaundice at a tertiary hospital in South Western Nigeria

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Abstract:

Introduction

Neonatal jaundice (NNJ) is a common problem in neonates. It is the clinical manifestation of elevated levels of (unconjugated) bilirubin in the body and occurs in 60% of term and 80% of preterm neonates within 1 week of birth¹. Despite recent advances in healthcare systems and increase in levels of information and community mobilisation, significant neonatal jaundice requiring hospitalisation remains a major health challenge in the developing world.

Although a preventable condition, severe NNJ is still a major cause of Cerebral Palsy in Sub-Saharan Africa², thus contributing immensely to loss of manpower to death and disability³, putting a strain on already scarce family and health care resources.

Data from the records of neonates who presented to our neonatal unit with NNJ was reviewed to provide an update on the incidence, risk factors, common causes, treatment modalities and outcomes among neonates presenting with neonatal jaundice.

Methods

It was a retrospective review of the case records of outborn babies presenting with jaundice between August 2018 and February 2019.

Results

Fifty-eight neonates presented with jaundice during the study period contributing 35.8% of total admissions. The male to female ratio was 1.9:1. The gestational age at birth ranged between 28-42 weeks. Forty-eight (82.8%) neonates were term with a mean weight at admission of 2.8 ± 0.7 kg. Modal age at presentation was 6days and time interval between onset of NNJ and hospital presentation ranged from 1 to 12days.

The mean (SD) of Total Serum bilirubin (TSB) at presentation was $20.4 (\pm 7.6)$ mg/dl (range 8.7 - 42.7mg/dl) and average (SD) peak TSB was $21.0 (\pm 7.9)$ mg/dl (range 9.7 - 46.3mg/dl).

About 39% of the mothers of the 41 neonates with TSB of at least 15mg/dl had Antenatal care at a secondary healthcare Centre while of the 23 neonates who presented more than 2days after onset of NNJ, 13 (56.5%) had mothers with a tertiary level of education.

About half of the babies had G6PD deficiency. One-third had a risk of ABO incompatibility and 6.4% had Rhesus incompatibility. Twenty-three (39.3%) had a positive sepsis screen.

All the neonates had phototherapy. Seventeen (23%) had double volume exchange blood transfusion and 7(4%) had treatment with Fresh Frozen Plasma. In-hospital mortality was 8% while 22.4% had neurologic features of bilirubin Encephalopathy at discharge.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the burden of Neonatal jaundice remains high. G6PD deficiency is the most common cause in our environment. Late presentation at health facilities is the most important risk factor for poor outcomes. Phototherapy and Exchange blood transfusions remain the mainstay of management, however, these are often technically impossible in resource constrained settings. Prevention of severe NNJ is therefore the choice means to curtail the perennial menace in resource limited settings.

Keywords:

Neonates, outborn, neonatal jaundice, bilirubin.

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